

Module 5	<u>Data infrastructures (DI)</u>
Course coordinator	Marco Prenassi (MP)
Lecturers	MP
Class Duration	21 hours
Module Description	This module discusses the main component of data infrastructure both on hardware and software side. Data lake concepts and practical implementation will be presented, discussed and used.
Main Topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The lower level: Ansible, Ceph, bucket, modern Filesystems features for data managing and resilience. - Infrastructure scalability (horizontal vs vertical) - Relational databases and SQL - Optimizing DB schema - ORM, SQLAlchemy - Rest API in flask - NoSQL databases - Data lake concepts and implementation - Data access control
Objectives	On successful completion of this module students should be able to understand the main concepts behind data infrastructure, interact properly with data infrastructures available to them and define their own requirements to consider when a data infrastructure is planned.